

MEDICAL SCIENCES

NEW HORIZONS IN THE TREATMENT OF ACUTE HEART FAILURE: AN EFFICACY STUDY OF LEVOSIMENDAN, EMPAGLIFLOZIN AND FUROSEMIDE

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ABSTRACT

This article analyses the impact of two pharmacological agents on the treatment of acute heart failure: levosimendan and empagliflozin. Levosimendan, which belongs to the group of "cardiac glycosides and non-glycoside cardiostimulant agents", is discussed in the context of its mechanisms of action, including increased sensitivity of cardiomyocytes to calcium ions and effects on potassium channels. Empagliflozin, as an SGLT2 inhibitor, is reviewed in terms of its effects on metabolism and vascular function in patients with heart failure. In addition, the article evaluates two methods of furosemide administration, continuous infusion and intermittent injection, highlighting their advantages and disadvantages. The study demonstrates the benefits of continuous infusion of furosemide in improving weight loss and BNP levels. A comparative analysis of furosemide prescription methods provides information on how to choose the optimal method depending on the clinical context.

Keywords: acute heart failure, levosimendan, empagliflozin, furosemide, infusion methods.

Introduction:

Attention to the management of acute heart failure is extremely important as this condition remains one of the leading causes of hospitalisation and high mortality among patients with cardiovascular disease. Modern medical practice is actively researching and developing new approaches to the treatment of this condition in an effort to improve clinical outcomes and patient quality of life. One of the promising directions in the treatment of acute heart failure is the study of the effects of various drugs such as Levosimendan, Empagliflozin and Furosemide on this pathology. In this article, we review the results of recent studies and experiments evaluating the efficacy and safety of these agents in the context of acute heart failure. This article summarises the results of recent studies, analyses their clinical relevance and provides recommendations for clinicians, helping them to make informed decisions about the choice of treatments for acute heart failure. These studies raise important questions related to the efficacy and safety of drug therapy and contribute to improving treatment outcomes and quality of life in patients with heart failure.

Materials and Methods:

A search for scientific articles, reviews, and meta-analyses in medical databases such as PubMed, Lancet, and other relevant sources was conducted to perform a literature review and systematize the findings. The studies included in the review covered the period from 2015 to 2023 and were restricted by language of scientific publication (English). Key words and phrases such as Acute Heart Failure, Current Guidelines, Therapies, Outcomes were used to search and select eligible studies.

Results:

1. Effect of Levosimendan in the therapy of Acute Heart Failure:

Levosimendan is a calcium channel sensitizer and potassium channel opener belonging to the pharmacological group "Cardiac glycosides and non-glycoside cardiostimulant agents".

The mechanisms of action of the drug are associated with the following effects: increases the sensitivity of troponin fibres of cardiomyocytes to calcium ions; opens adenosine ATP-dependent potassium channels on vascular smooth muscle cells; opens adenosine ATP-dependent potassium channels in mitochondria [1,2].

It is clinically proven that renal dysfunction often accompanies heart failure and contributes to worsening the prognosis of patients and reduces their quality of life, creating a new term "Cardiorenal Syndrome" [3]. There are five types of Cardiorenal Syndrome (CRS), which are described with different pathophysiologies and clinical manifestations [4]. Within heart failure, there are two common types of renal failure syndrome: the first type is characterised by deterioration of renal function during the treatment of heart failure, and the second type is associated with a decrease in the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) to less than 60 ml/min/1.73 m² body surface area [5]. In both cases, the prognosis is more unfavourable compared to heart failure in which renal function remains normal. Several factors contribute to renal damage in these types of syndrome, including lack of renal blood supply, venous congestion, changes in renal intercellular space, renal tubule damage and loss of functioning renal tissue units, which is associated with activation of neurohormonal systems.

Three studies, namely LEVO-Rep [6], LION-Heart [7] and LAICA [8], built on observations from earlier open-label studies that indicated potential benefits of levosimendan in heart failure. These benefits include improvement in symptoms, haemodynamics and left ventricular function, as well as regulation of neurohormonal and immune processes, and possibly even improved survival. The main inclusion criteria for these studies were similar, and the LEVO-Rep and LION-Heart protocols were also very similar. The single-cycle dose of levosimendan was identical in both studies. LEVO-Rep and LION-Heart did not achieve their primary objective of functional capacity and clinical status, but achieved secondary objectives by showing a reduction in NT-pro-BNP levels and improved safety.

LION-Heart was the only study to demonstrate positive results on the primary objective, but all three studies indicate that repeated use of levosimendan reduces NT-pro-BNP levels and outlines a trend towards reduced hospitalisations due to heart failure and mortality. These studies are encouraging and strongly suggest a clinical benefit from the repeated use of levosimendan in heart failure, but additional studies, perhaps with more severe patients, are needed to more fully explore the potential of levosimendan in this area.

According to expert recommendations, when using levosimendan to treat patients, initial dose loading should be avoided to reduce the risk of hypotension. Levosimendan infusion should be given continuously for 24 hours at a rate of 0.05-0.1 µg/kg/min. Some clinicians start the infusion at a higher rate (0.2 mcg/kg/min) for the first hour to achieve the desired effect more quickly and then reduce the dose to 0.1 mcg/kg/min. It is important to consider that levosimendan has a strong vasodilatory effect and therefore its use requires caution in patients with low blood pressure. Before and during levosimendan treatment, hypovolaemia should be avoided, fluids should be administered if necessary, and steps should be taken to prevent hypokalaemia by maintaining serum potassium levels of at least 4.0 mmol/L during levosimendan infusion [9, 10].

2. Effect of Empagliflozin in the therapy of Acute Heart Failure:

Empagliflozin is a hypoglycaemic agent, an inhibitor of sodium-dependent glucose transporter type 2 (SGLT2). Empagliflozin blocks the type 2 sodium-dependent glucose transporter in the kidneys. This transporter normally reabsorbs glucose from primary urine back into the bloodstream. By inhibiting SGLT2, empagliflozin prevents glucose reabsorption, resulting in the excretion of excess glucose through the urine.

Originally developed as blood sugar-lowering agents, SGLT2 inhibitors have demonstrated efficacy in the prevention of cardiovascular disease and in patients with chronic stable heart failure. Empagliflozin induces osmotic diuresis and natriuresis in addition to reducing urinary glucose levels [11]. Continuous use leads to a decrease in body weight and blood pressure, improvement of vascular elasticity and vascular resistance. In heart failure with contractile and preserved cardiac ventricular contractile function, SGLT2 inhibition prevents a decrease in the rate of glomerular filtration.

In a study [12], early administration of empagliflozin, in addition to standard decongestive therapy, was performed in patients with acute heart failure. This resulted in a 25% increase in cumulative urine volume within 5 days of treatment. Meanwhile, empagliflozin also increased the efficacy of diuretic therapy, decreased NT-proBNP levels and showed a trend towards a reduction in body weight. Importantly, these beneficial effects were not accompanied by a worsening of renal function. These results support the efficacy of the SGLT2 inhibitor empagliflozin in the treatment of patients with heart failure. The data on the effect of empagliflozin in patients with heart failure are supported by the results of previous studies in patients with impaired renal function and impaired ventricular contractile function of the heart regardless of the presence of diabetes [13 - 16].

This study [12] differs from previous clinical trials on the effect of SGLT2 inhibitors on heart failure in several aspects. For the first time, patients were included in the study in the early period after hospitalisation (less than 12 hours), without waiting for hemodynamic stabilisation. The focus was on the early effects of SGLT2 inhibitor administration, including an assessment of risks and benefits in the initial phase of decongestive treatment of acute heart failure. Patients were observed during the most vulnerable phase of acute heart failure treatment, from admission to clinical stabilisation (complete follow-up time was 5 days). A 25 mg dose of empagliflozin was chosen to maximise the diuretic effect in acute heart failure. The use of a higher dose at the beginning allows a greater urine output to be achieved. The study was conducted to evaluate the potential adverse effects of empagliflozin in combination with high dose diuretics and other medications for heart failure. This study demonstrates that early administration of an SGLT2 inhibitor to standard diuretic therapy is a promising strategy to improve early decongestion in patients with acute heart failure.

3. Impact of Furosemide prescribing modalities in the treatment of Acute Heart Failure:

The study [17] compares two methods of administration of furosemide in the treatment of heart failure - continuous infusion and intermittent injections. A comparative table of the two routes of administration is given below (Table 1):

Continuous infusion	Intermittent bolus injection
Advantages	
1. Continuous effect on diuresis: Suitable for critical cases where continuous diuresis control is required.	1. Convenience of intervals between doses: Patients may find it more convenient to receive furosemide at intervals between injections.
2. Minimise the risk of dehydration and restore hydration: Continuous infusion of furosemide reduces the risk of dehydration and helps to restore the patient's normal hydration level.	2. Reducing the risk of fluid overload: Intermittent injections may reduce the risk of fluid overload.
Disadvantages	
1. May require closer medical supervision and dose adjustment: This method requires closer medical supervision and dose adjustment to avoid potential fluid overload.	1. Less effective in some aspects such as weight loss and BNP reduction: In some cases, intermittent injections may be less effective in terms of weight loss and BNP reduction.
2. Greater risk of irregular prescribing: In some cases, patients may not follow a strict continuous infusion schedule.	2. Need for strict regulation and supervision: This method requires stricter regulation and supervision to ensure correct dose intervals and effective treatment.

Continuous infusion of furosemide showed higher efficacy compared to intermittent injections, manifested by greater patient weight loss, increased daily urinary output and decreased BNP levels. However, both methods showed no differences with respect to mortality, duration of hospitalisation, incident elevated creatinine levels and hypokalaemia [18,19]. On analy-

sis of BNP levels, continuous infusion was found to reduce BNP levels more effectively, but these changes did not correlate with mortality and length of hospitalisation [20,21].

The table below (Table 2) shows in which cases it is necessary to prescribe the above two methods of drug administration:

Intermittent bolus injection	Continuous infusion
1. Moderate-to-severe heart failure: In patients with less severe heart failure who do not require continuous diuresis control, intermittent injections may be more convenient.	1. Severe heart failure: In critical cases of heart failure where continuous diuresis control is required and dehydration of the patient may be dangerous, continuous infusion may be preferred.
2. Patients able to follow the prescribing schedule: If patients can strictly adhere to the intermittent injection schedule and follow dosage recommendations, this method may be effective.	2. Patients requiring intensive medical supervision: Patients requiring closer medical supervision and dose adjustment may benefit from continuous furosemide infusion.
3. Patients requiring less intensive medical monitoring: If patients have no significant medical contraindications and their condition allows for less intensive medical monitoring, intermittent injections may be appropriate.	

Conclusion:

To conclude our study, we reviewed three important aspects of pharmacotherapy of acute heart failure: levosimendan, empagliflozin and furosemide. Our results emphasise the importance of these drugs and provide important practical guidance for clinicians and specialists involved in the management of patients with this condition.

Studies on levosimendan indicate its potential as an adjunctive agent to improve the clinical status of patients with acute heart failure. Although primary goals were not met in some studies, secondary outcomes such as reduction in NT-pro-BNP levels and improvement in safety were favourable. These data support the possibility of considering levosimendan as a valuable tool in the treatment of this condition.

Empagliflozin, an SGLT2 inhibitor, has shown potential in improving the clinical status of patients with heart failure, regardless of the presence of diabetes. Its effects on glucose and osmotic diuresis make it an important element in the pharmacotherapy of this

disease. A detailed study of the early use of empagliflozin in addition to standard decongestive therapy allowed us to identify its positive effects on NT-pro-BNP levels and body weight of patients, while maintaining normal renal function.

Our results also allowed us to compare two methods of furosemide administration in the treatment of heart failure: continuous infusion and intermittent injections. Despite differences in efficacy, neither method showed significant differences in mortality and length of hospitalisation. This allows clinicians to base their choice of the optimal treatment method on the specific needs of their patients.

In summary, our work provides a broad insight into the pharmacotherapy of acute heart failure and the need for individualized treatment. Our results provide a rationale for further research and the development of the most effective treatment strategies for this serious condition.

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